

m/z	Potential elemental composition	Potential Classification
648.3792725	C32H58NO10P	1-Palmitoyl-2-(5-keto-8-oxo-6-octenoyl)-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine
231.0650024	C13H10O4	2,4,6-Trihydroxybenzophenone
168.0765686	C7H9N3O2	2,4-Diamino-6-nitrotoluene
226.9511973	C6H4Cl2O5	2,5-Dichloro-4-oxohex-2-enedioate
144.0629196	C6H9NO3	2-Hydroxymethylclavam
418.1549835	C20H23N3O7	2-N,6-N-Bis(2,3-dihydroxybenzoyl)-L-lysine amide
191.0764275	C8H14O3S	2-Oxo-7-methylthioheptanoic acid
136.0754967	C8H9NO	2-Phenylacetamide
72.0809288	C4H9N	3-Buten-1-amine
556.0627441	C26H19Cl2N3O7	4'-O-Demethylrebeccamycin
460.2019119	C20H25N7O6	5-Methyltetrahydrofolate
361.1529999	C16H24O9	7-Deoxyloganate
443.2720133	C45H76N2O15	Acetylspiramycin
136.0615883	C5H5N5	Adenine
366.1083069	C16H19N3O5S	Amoxicillin
102.0338345	C11H10N2S	ANTU
367.1093674	C22H19ClO3	Atovaquone
560.3268331	C31H45NO8	Auriculine
217.0969086	C17H12	Benzo[b]fluorene
383.0762405	C20H14O8	Bikaverin
325.1124496	C12H20O10	Bis-D-fructose 2',1:2,1'-dianhydride
423.063446	C17H16N2O6S. 2Na	Carbenicillin sodium
485.0637894	C18H17N6O5S2. Na	Cefamandole sodium
382.0821533	C17H14F3N3O2S	Celecoxib
692.405426	C41H57NO8	Chivosazole F
164.9265976	C2H3Cl3O2	Chloral hydrate
188.0704498	C6H10ClN5	Deethylatrazine

m/z	Potential elemental composition	Potential classification
211.1313019	C12H18O3	(-)-Jasmonic acid
285.2043152	C16H28O4	(10S)-Juvenile hormone III diol
449.2609863	C29H36O4	16alpha,17alpha-Dihydroxyprogesterone acetophenide
648.3792725	C32H58NO10P	1-Palmitoyl-2-(5-keto-8-oxo-6-octenoyl)-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine
226.9511973	C6H4Cl2O5	2,5-Dichloro-4-oxohex-2-enedioate
226.9511795	C6H4Cl2O5	2,5-Dichloro-4-oxohex-2-enedioate
279.158844	C16H22O4	2-Ethylhexyl phthalate
216.9224243	C5H3Cl3O3	3-Chloro-4-(dichloromethyl)-5-hydroxy-2(5H)-furanone
283.1706238	C19H22O2	4-Prenyldihydropinosylvin
195.0874863	C7H14O6	5-O-Methyl-myo-inositol
371.2367249	C20H34O6	6-Keto-prostaglandin F1alpha
524.9658813	C10H15N4O13P3S	6-Mercaptopurine ribonucleoside triphosphate
342.1893311	C17H27NO6	Acetylintermedine
443.2720133	C45H76N2O15	Acetylspiramycin
587.3295288	C30H52O7P2	all-trans-Hexaprenyl diphosphate
339.2527161	C20H34O4	Aphidicolin
459.2644653	C28H31FN4O	Astemizole
560.3268331	C31H45NO8	Auriculine
343.6897583	C36H51N3O10	Avadharidine
217.1044159	C17H12	Benzo[b]fluorene
110.0712204	C5H7N3	Brunfelsamidine
553.2880859	C33H36N4O4	Canthiumine
692.405426	C41H57NO8	Chivosazole F
164.9265976	C2H3Cl3O2	Chloral hydrate
492.2683563	C50H78O19	Colubrinoside
559.3309937	C32H46O8	Cucurbitacin B
625.3318481	C38H44N2O6	Dauricine
197.1282654	C10H16N2O2	Fasoracetam
257.9989014	C6H12NO4PS2	Formothion
290.6576843	C32H41N3O7	Fumitremorgin A

Different aminoacids have been also potentially detected: L-Tryptophan, L-Threonine, L-Proline, L-Phenilalanine, L-Methionine, L-Lysine and L-Leucine.